

KNOWSKITE-X

Knowledge-driven fine-tuning of perovskite-based electrode materials for reversible Chemicals-to-Power devices

Multiscale Modelling Workflows for Solid Oxide Cells: A MODA-Based Framework

Project Information

Grant Agreement Number	101091534
Project Full Title	Knowledge-driven fine-tuning of perovskite-based electrode materials for reversible Chemicals-to-Power devices
Project Acronym	KNOWSKITE-X
Funding scheme	RIA
Start date of the project	1 st January 2023
Duration	48 months
Project Coordinator	Elise Berrier (CNRS)
Project Website	https://knowskite-x.eu/

Document Information

Associated deliverable n°	D4.4 - Modelling and characterisation workflows
Document title	Multiscale Modelling Workflows for Solid Oxide Cells: A MODA-Based Framework
Authors	Andrea Prieto Pabón, Macarena García Ayala (IDENER.AI)
Contributors	Centre national de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) Università degli Studi di Padova (UNIPD) Know Center (KNOW)

Document Log

Version	Date	Description of Change
V1.0	16/03/2026	First draft
V1.1	06/04/2026	Final version
V1.2		

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1 Executive Summary

This document presents the application of the MODA (MOdelling DAta generalisation) framework to describe and organise the multiscale modelling activities developed within the KNOWSKITE-X project. MODA provides a structured way to document models, their inputs and outputs, and the relationships between different modelling scales.

By applying this methodology, the modelling workflows become clearer and easier to communicate across different communities, including industrial stakeholders, software developers, and modelling experts.

The document compiles the MODA workflows associated with the main modelling approaches used in the project, including density functional theory (DFT), kinetic modelling, continuum-scale simulations, and hybrid machine-learning–DFT approaches. It also highlights how these models are connected within a multiscale modelling strategy.

2 Introduction

This document presents a structured framework for describing multiscale modelling workflows using the MODA (MOdelling DAta generalisation) methodology. The objective is to provide a clear and transparent representation of how different modelling approaches interact across scales, from electronic-structure calculations to continuum simulations.

The use of MODA helps ensure consistency, transparency, and interoperability between models developed by different partners and scientific communities. It also facilitates communication between industrial stakeholders, software developers, and modelling experts.

The document introduces the MODA methodology and illustrates its application to several modelling approaches used to study perovskite-based systems, including electronic-structure calculations, kinetic modelling, continuum simulations, and hybrid machine-learning approaches.

The work presented in this document contributes to the development of harmonised modelling workflows for the study of perovskite-based materials and devices. The modelling activities integrate several approaches across different scales, combining electronic-structure calculations, kinetic modelling, and continuum simulations.

These modelling efforts are closely connected with experimental activities in order to ensure that the models capture the most relevant physical and chemical phenomena and can be used to interpret and guide experimental observations.

3 Role of Modelling in Materials Development

3.1 Models and simulations

Modelling is a powerful tool for understanding and describing complex physical and chemical processes. By defining mathematical representations of a system, models help identify the key parameters controlling its behaviour and provide insights into how the system evolves under different conditions.

Simulation complements modelling by providing the numerical solution of these mathematical formulations for specific scenarios. Through simulations, it is possible to predict system behaviour, analyse trends, and explore conditions that may be difficult or expensive to investigate experimentally (Figure 3-1).

Figure 3-1. Relationship between modelling, simulation and experimental validation.

In practice, modelling and simulation are most effective when combined with experimental work. Continuous feedback between theoretical modelling and experimental observations helps ensure that models capture the most relevant mechanisms and parameters governing the system.

3.2 Industrial relevance of modelling and simulation

Modelling and simulation are increasingly used in industry to support the development, optimisation, and deployment of new materials and technologies. By providing predictive insights into the behaviour of complex systems, modelling can reduce the need for costly and time-consuming experimental campaigns.

In materials research, modelling helps establish relationships between chemical composition, microstructure, and macroscopic properties. This capability is particularly valuable for accelerating the design of new materials and optimising existing ones for emerging applications.

As a result, modelling and simulation can significantly shorten development cycles, reduce costs associated with trial-and-error experimentation, and support more efficient innovation processes.

3.3 Impact of modelling on materials innovation

Modelling plays a central role in modern materials research and engineering. It supports the understanding of complex physical and chemical phenomena across multiple scales, from the electronic structure of materials to the behaviour of devices and systems.

By complementing experimental work, modelling enables researchers and engineers to:

- Guide experimental design and identify promising research directions.
- Interpret experimental observations and uncover underlying mechanisms.
- Explore operating conditions that may be difficult to investigate experimentally.
- Accelerate the development and optimisation of materials and technologies.

These capabilities contribute to reducing development time, improving process efficiency, and enabling more sustainable technological solutions.

4 MODA (MOdelling DAta generalisation)

The increasing use of modelling and simulation in materials research requires a clear and consistent way to document models, workflows, and data exchange between different modelling approaches. To address this need, the European Materials Modelling Council developed the MODA (Modelling Data Generalisation) framework, which provides a structured methodology for describing modelling and simulation activities.

MODA aims to improve communication and interoperability between different stakeholders involved in modelling activities, including industrial end-users, software developers, and theoretical researchers. By providing a common structure for describing models, simulations, and workflows, MODA helps ensure transparency, reproducibility, and consistency in multi-scale modelling projects.

A central component of this framework is the **MODA fiche**¹, a structured documentation template that captures the key elements required to describe a modelling workflow. The fiche provides information ranging from the user case and system description to the computational implementation of the model.

Further details about the MODA methodology and templates can be found through the documentation provided by the EMMC².

Within this framework, modelling workflows are typically represented as a sequence of interconnected models, where the output of one model becomes the input of another. Different types of workflows can exist depending on how models interact, including:

- **Sequential workflows**, where models are executed one after another (Figure 4-1).
- **Iterative workflows**, where feedback loops refine results through repeated calculations (Figure 4-2).
- **Tightly coupled workflows**, where models interact dynamically during the simulation process (Figure 4-3).

Figure 4-1. Consecutive workflow – Linked models

Figure 4-2. Iterative workflow

¹ M. templates, 17 01 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://emmc.eu/moda-chada/moda/#moda-templates>

² E. Commision, What makes a material function? Let me compute the ways..., Modelling in H2020 LEIT-NMBP Programme. Materials and Nanotechnology projects, Sixth version, 2017. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/e0845ae1-1b60-11e7-aeb3-01aa75ed71a1>

Figure 4-3. Tightly coupled models

4.1 Model types

In multiscale modelling, models can be classified according to the physical entity whose behaviour is described, rather than only by their characteristic spatial or temporal scales. This classification helps clarify the role of each model within a modelling workflow.

Four main model categories are commonly considered:

4.1.1 Electronic models

Electronic models describe the behaviour of **electrons** using quantum mechanical approaches. These models provide highly accurate descriptions of material properties at the fundamental level and are widely used to investigate electronic structure, chemical bonding, and reaction mechanisms. Typical applications include:

- Electronic band structure calculations.
- Thermodynamic stability of defects and dopants.
- Calculation of reaction energies and activation barriers

4.1.2 Atomistic model

Atomistic models describe the behaviour of **atoms and molecules**, typically using classical or semi-empirical approaches. These models allow the investigation of atomic motion, structural organisation, and dynamic processes at the nanoscale. Examples include:

- Molecular dynamics simulations
- Evaluation of surface and interface energies
- Analysis of dynamical and spectral properties

4.1.3 Mesoscopic model

Mesoscopic models describe the behaviour of larger entities, such as nanoparticles, grains, or domains, without explicitly resolving atomic-scale details. These models are useful for studying collective phenomena and structural evolution at intermediate scales. Typical applications include:

- Morphology evolution and domain formation.
- Growth kinetics and aggregation processes
- Thermal or magnetic behaviour of structured materials

4.1.4 Continuum model

Continuum models describe materials as continuous media, ignoring their discrete atomic structure. These models are widely used to simulate macroscopic behaviour and are commonly applied in engineering and industrial applications. Typical examples include:

- Heat and mass transport.
- Chemical reaction kinetics.
- Fluid dynamics and electromagnetic behaviour.

In practice, the choice of model depends on the balance between **accuracy, computational cost, and the scale of the phenomena being studied**. Multiscale workflows often combine several of these model types to capture different aspects of a system.

The main properties of the different models are shown in Table 1 and Figure 4-4. As it can be seen, the smaller the entity whose behaviour is described through the model, the smaller the indicative length and the time scales.

Table 1. Main properties of the different models

Model	Entity whose behaviour is described	Indicative length scale	Indicative time scale
Electronic models	Electron	0.1-1.0 nm	-
Atomistic model	Atom	0.1-100 nm	fs - μm
Mesosopic model	Nanoparticle, molecule, grain, bed, etc.	1 nm - 100 μm	ms - s
Continuum model	Continuum volume	nm - m	s - ks

Figure 4-4. Different model types depending on their length and time scales

4.2 Data exchange and post-processing in modelling workflows

One of the key challenges in multiscale modelling is the transfer of information between models operating at different scales. In MODA workflows, this transfer is typically achieved through post-processing operations.

Post-processing refers to the analysis and transformation of the raw outputs produced by a simulation in order to extract quantities that can be used as inputs for subsequent models. These operations may include statistical analysis, parameter extraction, averaging procedures, or other data-processing methods.

It is important to distinguish between:

- **model equations**, which generate the physical state of the system during simulation, and
- **post-processing operations**, which analyse the simulation outputs to obtain derived quantities.

In multiscale workflows, the results produced by post-processing steps often serve as the **linking variables** that connect different models. These variables enable information to flow across modelling scales, allowing complex systems to be described through interconnected simulations.

The following sections describe how the MODA framework was applied within the KNOWSKITE-X project to document and structure the multiscale modelling workflows developed during the project.

5 Application of the MODA framework in the KNOWSKITE-X project

The MODA framework was applied in the KNOWSKITE-X project to document and structure the multiscale modelling workflow developed to study electrochemical processes in perovskite-based materials.

An initial conceptual workflow was defined at the beginning of the project to represent the expected interaction between modelling scales. During the execution of the work and the collection of modelling data, this workflow was progressively refined. The updated workflow reflects the final modelling strategy adopted in the project.

Figure 5-1 shows the initial conceptual workflow, while Figure 5-2 presents the final MODA workflow implemented in the project.

Figure 5-1: Foreseen MODA workflow for the articulation between electronic and mesoscopic levels.

The modelling strategy combines several complementary modelling approaches operating at different physical scales. In total, **four modelling components** are included in the workflow:

- **Model 1 – Electronic / Atomistic model:** Density Functional Theory (DFT) simulations - [Centre national de la Recherche Scientifique \(CNRS\)](#)
- **Model 2 – Mesoscopic model:** Microkinetic modelling of electrode reactions - [Università degli Studi di Padova \(UNIPD\)](#)
- **Model 3 – Continuum model:** Large-scale system modelling - [IDENER.AI \(IDENER\)](#)
- **Data-based model:** Hybrid Machine Learning / DFT approach - [Know Center \(KNOW\)](#)

The table below provides a high-level overview of the simulation workflow, including the user case, the chain of models involved, and the rationale behind their selection.

OVERVIEW OF THE SIMULATION	
USER CASE	This simulation aims to model the electrochemical activity and performance of electrode materials for solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC) and solid oxide electrolysis cells (SOEC). The focus is on understanding the atomic-scale structure and reactivity of active sites, the kinetics of electrochemical reactions, and mass and heat transfer at different scales to optimise electrode design and operation conditions. The study is particularly relevant for improving energy efficiency and material stability in electrochemical devices under real operating conditions.
CHAIN OF MODELS	MODEL 1 (Electronic / Atomistic): DFT Modelling (CNRS)
	MODEL 2 (Mesoscopic): Kinetic Modelling (UNIPD)
	MODEL 3 (Continuum): Large-Scale Modelling (IDE)
	DATA-BASED MODEL (Hybrid DFT/ML Model): Machine Learning Integration (KNOW)
PUBLICATION PEER-REVIEWING THE DATA	The dataset and simulation results will be documented in scientific publications, ensuring the quality and reproducibility of the data. Relevant journals and conferences in materials science, electrochemistry, and computational modelling will be targeted for publication. But, up to date, the <u>models are still under development</u> .
ACCESS CONDITIONS	<p>Models & Data: A combination of open-source and proprietary software.</p> <p><i>Electronic and Atomistic</i> models are based on DFT+U calculations to describe the electronic structure of perovskite surfaces, accounting for the magnetic properties of the solids. All calculations at this scale use periodic DFT software—such as VASP, CASTEP, CP2K, or Quantum ESPRESSO—to compute the electron density of 3D crystals (bulk or surfaces) using supercell methods. By calculating surface energies from slabs cut along various orientations in the bulk, we identify the most stable surfaces and propose active sites for catalysis. In a second step, a reaction mechanism is proposed, combining experimental data and classical elementary surface reaction mechanisms. The calculation of reaction energies (for thermodynamic insights) and activation energies (for kinetic insights) provides input data for larger-scale modelling. <i>Mesoscopic</i> model will be developed using COMSOL Multiphysics®. It numerically solves mass balances of species in different phases (gas, solid surface, solid lattice), discretising a mono-dimensional representation of the electrode/cell either accounting from time evolution of the dependent variables (to simulate EIS techniques) or at steady-state, to gather information on variables useful to cell design or to better understand the chemistry and physics of the device. <i>Continuum models</i> numerically solve mass, momentum, and energy balances—typically using finite volume or element methods—by discretizing the electrochemical reactor into regions and cells where key variables like pressure, velocity, and concentration are updated over time based on governing equations and defined boundary conditions. <i>Hybrid DFT/ML Model:</i> Interfacing libraries and the material database for this model are implemented in Python code using open-source modules. Data is managed using the “pandas” module, data preprocessing is performed using the “scikit-learn” module. The ML model itself is implemented using “NumPy”.</p> <p>Owner: Research institutions involved in KNOWSKITE-X project, WP2 (CNRS, UNIPD, IDENER, KNOW).</p> <p>Repository: Data will be stored in KNOWSKITE-X GitHub repository and data platform</p>

<p>WORKFLOW AND ITS RATIONALE</p>	<p>This workflow bridges multiple scales (electronic/atomistic → mesoscopic → continuum) to translate atomic-scale material properties into macroscopic performance predictions. The chosen approach allows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Atomic-scale insight from DFT to guide the selection of active materials. 2. Reaction kinetics modelling to predict electrode performance under real conditions. 3. Stack-level simulations to optimise large-scale operation. 4. Machine learning-assisted optimization for improved efficiency in material discovery and process simulation. <p>The combination of physics-based and data-driven models enhances predictive accuracy, enabling a rational design of next-generation SOFC/SOEC electrodes.</p>
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The diagram in Figure 5-2 illustrates the overall modelling workflow and the interactions between the different modelling levels. Outputs generated at one level are processed and transferred as inputs to subsequent models, enabling the integration of information across scales.

Figure 5-2: MODA workflow connecting electronic, mesoscopic and continuum modelling levels.

5.1 Electronic / Atomistic model: DFT modelling of active centres

Understanding the structural and catalytic properties of perovskite electrode materials is a key objective of the KNOWSKITE-X modelling activities. In particular, the behaviour of active surface sites plays a central role in determining the performance of electrochemical reactions.

Although the bulk structure of many perovskite materials is well characterised, the stability and reactivity of their exposed surfaces — especially under operating conditions involving water and reactive gases — remain less well understood. For this reason, Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations are used to investigate the structure and activity of relevant surfaces at the atomic scale.

The DFT simulations aim to characterise the binding configurations and energetics of species involved in electrochemical reactions. Materials considered include doped perovskite compositions such as:

- $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{FeO}_3$ (LSF)
- $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{La}_x\text{Ti}_{1-y}\text{Fe}_y\text{O}_3$

These simulations provide detailed information on:

- adsorption energies of reaction species
- reaction pathways and intermediates
- activation energies of elementary reaction steps
- identification of rate-determining processes

In addition, vibrational spectra of relevant intermediates are calculated to support comparison with experimental characterisation techniques such as in-situ Raman and FTIR spectroscopy.

Because DFT simulations are computationally demanding, the number of candidate systems explored is progressively reduced to focus on the most promising materials. Selected configurations are then further analysed and integrated with machine-learning approaches to accelerate the exploration of additional material compositions.

Figure 5-3. Model 1 - Electronic/Atomistic modelling (CNRS)

ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED		
MODEL 1 (Electronic / Atomistic) DFT Modelling	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	Determination of the reaction mechanism for OER HER on LSCF perovskites depending on the nature of the catalytic site and on the electrode potential.
	MATERIAL	La _(1-x) Sr _x Fe _(1-y) Co _y O ₃ perovskites
	GEOMETRY	Perovskite surface will be model using periodic calculations using cells containing around 100 atoms.
	TIME LAPSE	Static DFT calculations
	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	Calculations are performed at T=0 K and P= 0 bar.
	PUBLICATIONS ON THIS DATA	n.a.

MODEL EQUATION				
MODEL 1 (Electronic / Atomistic) DFT Modelling	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Classical DFT+U.		
	MODEL ENTITY	Electrons and atoms.		
	MODEL PHYSICS EQUATIONS	EQUATION	Resolution of the Khon-Sham equation.	
		PHYSICAL QUANTITIES	Energy, one electron orbitals, Forces	
	MATERIAL RELATIONS	RELATION	PAW pseudo potential to describe core electrons, plane wave basis set	
		PHYSICAL QUANTITIES	Electron density matrix around nucleus	
SIMULATED INPUT	Input: Perovskites unit cell based on cif file. Output: Reaction and Activation energies of the elementary surface step. Effect of the electrode potential on the energies.			

SOLVER AND TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS		
MODEL 1 (Electronic / Atomistic) DFT	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Iterative resolution of Khon-Shan equation
	SOFTWARE TOOL	Vasp (https://www.vasp.at/)
	TIME STEP	Time is not included in the calculation

	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION	Kohn-Sham $\left(-\frac{\Delta}{2m} + V_{ext} + V_H + V_{xc}\right)\varphi_i = \varepsilon_i \varphi_i$
		MATERIAL RELATIONS	Augmented wave pseudopotential are used to describe core/valence electrons interactions
		MATERIAL	La _x Sr _(1-x) Co _y Fe _(1-y) O ₃ ; La _x Sr _(1-x) Ni _y Fe _(1-y) O ₃
	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	Periodic boundary condition: calculation on infinite slabs	
ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	Variation of electronic energy below 1E-6		

MODEL 1 (Electronic / Atomistic) DFT	POST-PROCESSING	
	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	Reaction mechanism and activation energies. Estimation of the electrode overpotential
	METHODOLOGIES	Statistical thermodynamic correction to compute electrode potential
	MARGIN OF ERROR	Accuracy of the activation energies is below 10% (0,1 eV for value close to 1 eV)

5.2 Mesoscopic model: microkinetic modelling of electrode reactions

Results obtained from the atomistic simulations are used to construct a mesoscopic-scale model describing the kinetics of electrochemical reactions occurring at the electrode surface.

The goal of this model is to translate the microscopic insights obtained from DFT calculations into predictions that can be compared with experimental measurements at the device scale.

The modelling strategy is based on a **microkinetic description of the surface reaction network**, including adsorption, reaction, and desorption processes occurring at active catalytic sites. The model explicitly accounts for:

- concentrations of gas-phase species
- electron and ion transport
- surface coverage of reaction intermediates
- reaction rates and activation barriers

Kinetic parameters such as activation energies, pre-exponential factors, and adsorption coefficients are derived from the electronic-structure calculations performed in the previous modelling stage.

The microkinetic model is integrated into a **one-dimensional electrochemical cell model**, allowing the simulation of device-level quantities such as:

- current-voltage (I-V) characteristics
- polarization losses

- electrochemical efficiency

This approach enables a direct connection between material properties, reaction mechanisms, and the overall electrochemical performance of the cell.

The modelling work includes two main steps:

1. Development of the kinetic model describing reaction mechanisms and transport phenomena.
2. Calibration and refinement of model parameters using experimental data generated within the project.

Figure 5-4: Model 2 - Kinetic (mesoscopic) modelling (UNIPD)

ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED	
MODEL 2 (Mesoscopic): Kinetic Modelling (UNIPD)	<p>ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED</p> <p>Physical, chemical and electrochemical phenomena describing the processes occurring at the single electrodes of a fuel cell/electrolyser:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gaseous species diffusion - Gaseous species (dissociative) adsorption on electrode surface - Adsorbed species surface diffusion and surface reactions - Electrochemical reactions on the electrode surface - Charge transfer to/into the electrode/electrolyte system
	<p>MATERIAL</p> <p>Ni-8YSZ, LSCF as electrodes, 8YSZ, CGO as electrolytes</p>
	<p>GEOMETRY</p> <p>Electrode (30 μm thickness), electrolyte (1.5 mm thickness)</p>
	<p>TIME LAPSE</p> <p>Seconds</p>
	<p>MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS</p> <p>Fixed external pressure, imposed voltage and fixed gas composition at the electrode entrance</p>
	<p>PUBLICATIONS ON THIS DATA</p> <p>n. a.</p>

MODEL EQUATION		
MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Thermodynamics, chemistry reaction (microkinetic) model, electr(ron)ics	
MODEL ENTITY	Finite volumes	
MODEL PHYSICS EQUATIONS	EQUATION	<p>1. Gaseous species mass conservation</p> $\varepsilon \frac{\partial c_i}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_i + r_i$ $\mathbf{J}_i = -D_i^{eff} \nabla c_i$ <p>2. Adsorbed species mass conservation</p> $S_{kl} \frac{\partial c_i^{ads}}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_i^{ads} + r_i$ $\mathbf{J}_i^{ads} = -S_{kl} D_i^{surf} \nabla c_i^{ads}$ $c_i^{ads} = \Gamma_{sites} \theta_i$ <p>3. Electronic and ionic charge balances</p> $S_{el-io} C_{al} \frac{\partial (\varphi_{el} - \varphi_{io})}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (-\sigma_{el}^{eff} \nabla \varphi_{el}) + nF r_{el}$ $S_{el-io} C_{al} \frac{\partial (\varphi_{el} - \varphi_{io})}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (-\sigma_{io}^{eff} \nabla \varphi_{io}) + nF r_{io}$
	PHYSICAL QUANTITIES	<p>1. Gaseous species concentration c_i</p> <p>2. Adsorbed species coverage θ_i</p> <p>3. Electric and ionic potentials φ_{el} and φ_{io}</p>
MATERIAL RELATIONS	RELATION	Percolation theory
	PHYSICAL QUANTITIES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Double phase boundary surface per unit volume (MIEC electrodes) - Triple phase boundary length per unit volume (composite electrodes) - Gas-ionic conductor contact surface per unit volume - Gas-electronic conductor contact surface per unit volume - Effective electrical/ionic conductivity
SIMULATED INPUT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thermodynamic properties of the gaseous and adsorbed species (enthalpies, entropies, adsorption/desorption equilibrium constants) - Composition, porosity and particle size of the electrodes - Electric/ionic bulk conductivity - Gaseous feed composition - FC/EC operating conditions (temperature, pressure, voltage) 	

MODEL 2 (Mesoscopic): Kinetic Modelling (UNIPD)

SOLVER AND TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS																		
MODEL 2 (Mesoscopic): Kinetic Modelling (UNIPD)	<table border="1"> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">NUMERICAL SOLVER</td> <td>MUMPS (Multifrontal Massively Parallel Solver) for stationary simulations BDF (Backward Differentiation Formula) for time dependent simulations</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">SOFTWARE TOOL</td> <td>COMSOL Multiphysics</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">TIME STEP</td> <td>Ranging from 0.05 s to 1 s</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="3" style="text-align: center;">COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION</td> <td style="text-align: center;">PHYSICS EQUATION</td> <td>The electrode or the cell domains (electrodes, electrolyte, gas channel) are discretised into smaller domains where the equations are solved using specific meshes, regular and made by small segments (about 1/100 of the corresponding domain length) for 1D simulations, and random triangular for the 2D simulations. Depending on the simulation dimension (0D,1D, 2D) the electrode is represented by a single point, a segment and a rectangular surface respectively. Properties of the electrode are accordingly assumed homogeneous using effective properties.</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">MATERIAL RELATIONS</td> <td>Explicit time discretization for ODE, spatial discretisation for PDE, according to Finite Element Methods</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">MATERIAL</td> <td>Explicit time discretisation for ODE, spatial discretisation for PDE, according to Finite Element Methods</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS</td> <td>Axial symmetry for pseudo-3D simulations Dirichlet Boundary Conditions/No flux for the charge and mass balances</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS</td> <td>Convergence criteria: relative tolerance <math> < 10^{-4}</math></td> </tr> </table>	NUMERICAL SOLVER	MUMPS (Multifrontal Massively Parallel Solver) for stationary simulations BDF (Backward Differentiation Formula) for time dependent simulations	SOFTWARE TOOL	COMSOL Multiphysics	TIME STEP	Ranging from 0.05 s to 1 s	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION	The electrode or the cell domains (electrodes, electrolyte, gas channel) are discretised into smaller domains where the equations are solved using specific meshes, regular and made by small segments (about 1/100 of the corresponding domain length) for 1D simulations, and random triangular for the 2D simulations. Depending on the simulation dimension (0D,1D, 2D) the electrode is represented by a single point, a segment and a rectangular surface respectively. Properties of the electrode are accordingly assumed homogeneous using effective properties.	MATERIAL RELATIONS	Explicit time discretization for ODE, spatial discretisation for PDE, according to Finite Element Methods	MATERIAL	Explicit time discretisation for ODE, spatial discretisation for PDE, according to Finite Element Methods	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	Axial symmetry for pseudo-3D simulations Dirichlet Boundary Conditions/No flux for the charge and mass balances	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	Convergence criteria: relative tolerance <math> < 10^{-4}</math>
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ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	Convergence criteria: relative tolerance <math> < 10^{-4}</math>																	

POST PROCESSING					
MODEL 2 (Mesoscopic): Kinetic Modelling (UNIPD)	<table border="1"> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">THE PROCESSED OUTPUT</td> <td>Local maps for gaseous and adsorbed species composition Local maps for ionic and electronic potential Polarisation curves for stationary simulations Nyquist and Bode plot for time dependent problems</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">METHODOLOGIES</td> <td>Local maps are a direct outcome of the simulator, and no post-processing is needed. The same holds for polarisation curves, resulting from a parametric sweep on the voltage imposed to the cell or from the overvoltage imposed to the single electrode. Nyquist plots are obtained with two different methods (leading the same results): the first requires the fitting of the sinusoidal responses (voltage/overvoltage, current density) to get amplitude and phase shift, that are then employed in the impedance calculation. The other uses Fast Fourier Transform (FFT method) to directly compute the impedance without any fitting, reducing the possibility of error related to bad fitting of the sinusoids.</td> </tr> </table>	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	Local maps for gaseous and adsorbed species composition Local maps for ionic and electronic potential Polarisation curves for stationary simulations Nyquist and Bode plot for time dependent problems	METHODOLOGIES	Local maps are a direct outcome of the simulator, and no post-processing is needed. The same holds for polarisation curves, resulting from a parametric sweep on the voltage imposed to the cell or from the overvoltage imposed to the single electrode. Nyquist plots are obtained with two different methods (leading the same results): the first requires the fitting of the sinusoidal responses (voltage/overvoltage, current density) to get amplitude and phase shift, that are then employed in the impedance calculation. The other uses Fast Fourier Transform (FFT method) to directly compute the impedance without any fitting, reducing the possibility of error related to bad fitting of the sinusoids.
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MARGIN OF ERROR	Errors related to particle idealization (e.g. assumed as spherical). Uncertainties in structural, textural and morphological properties of the electrodes.
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5.3 Continuum model: stack-level system modelling

At the largest scale of the modelling workflow, continuum modelling is used to simulate the behaviour of complete electrochemical systems relevant to Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFC) and Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cells (SOEC).

This model extends the analysis from individual cells to **multi-cell stack configurations**, including the interaction between several structural components such as:

- electrochemical cells
- interconnects
- sealing elements
- gas flow channels

The model captures macroscopic transport processes including:

- mass transport of reactants and products
- heat transfer within the stack
- electrochemical energy conversion

By analysing these processes, the model provides insights into system-level behaviour and helps identify optimal operating conditions. In particular, the simulations support the evaluation of thermal management strategies and the identification of conditions that could lead to performance degradation.

If required, additional mechanical simulations can be incorporated to evaluate stress distribution within the stack and assess the risk of structural damage under operating conditions.

The results of this modelling stage contribute to the design and optimisation of prototype systems and support the interpretation of experimental tests performed at the device level.

Figure 5-5: Model 3 – Large-Scale (continuum) modelling (IDE)

ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED					
MODEL 3 (Continuum): Large-Scale Modelling	<table border="1"> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED</td> <td>Flow characteristics (pressure, temperature, species concentration) and heat concentration and dissipation on stacked fuel and electrochemical cells.</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">MATERIAL</td> <td>The materials currently tested are based on Perovskites with different contents of Ba, La, Sr, Ca, Mn, Fe, Ni, and O for the cathode; YSZ-Ni materials for the anode; and YSZ for the electrolyte.</td> </tr> </table>	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	Flow characteristics (pressure, temperature, species concentration) and heat concentration and dissipation on stacked fuel and electrochemical cells.	MATERIAL	The materials currently tested are based on Perovskites with different contents of Ba, La, Sr, Ca, Mn, Fe, Ni, and O for the cathode; YSZ-Ni materials for the anode; and YSZ for the electrolyte.
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MATERIAL	The materials currently tested are based on Perovskites with different contents of Ba, La, Sr, Ca, Mn, Fe, Ni, and O for the cathode; YSZ-Ni materials for the anode; and YSZ for the electrolyte.				

	GEOMETRY	Stacked cells as depicted in the Figure below, in cm (the geometry might change during the evolution of the project, and this might be considered an example).
	TIME LAPSE	The simulation time will depend on the process activation energies and will run until convergence, but we expected to be in the range of seconds (s).
	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	Solid Oxide Fuell or Electrochemical cell operation.
	PUBLICATIONS ON THIS DATA	No publications available at the current stage of the project. (n. a.)

MODEL 3 (Continuum): Large-Scale Modelling (IDE)	MODEL EQUATION		
	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuous model	
	MODEL ENTITY	Finite elements.	
	MODEL PHYSICS EQUATIONS	EQUATION	Generic transport equation: $\frac{d\rho\phi}{dt} + \nabla \cdot (\rho\vec{u}\phi) = \nabla \cdot \vec{q}_\phi + S_\phi$ For mass, heat, and momentum.
		PHYSICAL QUANTITIES	$\phi = Y$ where Y are the species concentration, $\vec{q}_Y = -D\nabla Y$ (Fick Law). In this case, S_Y would be defined according to the Butler-Volmer equation and will consider the reaction energies and barriers. $\phi = T$ where T is the temperature, $\vec{q}_T = -k\nabla T$ (Fourier's Law). In this case, S_T would be defined according Ohmic losses and the reaction enthalpy. In the case of momentum, the equation becomes Navier-Stokes.
	MATERIAL RELATIONS	RELATION	All the material relations will be considered in pre-exponential factors for reaction rates, diffusion constants and porosity will be taken into account on the Fick Law, thermal conductivity will be considered on the Fourier Law, and reaction enthalpies will be considered inside the S_T term.
		PHYSICAL QUANTITIES	SBET of the catalyst, permeability, viscosity, diffusion constant on the pore, reaction energies, enthalpies (for heat transport) and barriers on the different catalysts.

	SIMULATED INPUT	The inputs coming from other simulations are the reaction energies and barriers for all relevant chemical reactions, diffusion constants in the pores and on the surface of the material (all of them from DFT), apparent activation energies, and the identification of the most relevant steps in the reaction network (last two from mesoscopic model).
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MODEL 3 (Continuum): Large-Scale Modelling (IDE)	SOLVER AND TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS		
	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Finite elements.	
	SOFTWARE TOOL	COMSOL	
	TIME STEP	To be determined, probably adaptative until reach steady state.	
	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION	The equations are discretised into Partial Differential Equations (PDEs) using the finite elements method.
		MATERIAL RELATIONS	Hardcoded as function of discretised space-time variables (e.g. reactions rates, heat flux...)
		MATERIAL	The material is meshed into a given number of cells and each one of them is a discrete domain where PDEs are solved.
	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	The computational boundary conditions will be determined in the future, but the following patches will be defined: External walls, Inlet, outlet, and cell. Then, for each cell, a cathode, an anode, and an electrolyte patch will be defined. Each stacked cell will be connected through gas channels. Thermal boundaries will be applied such as convective heat loss boundaries.	
ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	COMSOL default values, which will be fine tuned if required.		

MODEL 3 (Continuum): Large-Scale Modelling	POST PROCESSING	
	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	Process conversion, generated current density, and heat generation and dissipation in volume elements.
METHODOLOGIES	Conversion will be estimated from integrating the amount of Hydrogen in the inlet and outlet surfaces and define conversion as $X = 100 \cdot \frac{(H_{2in} - H_{2out})}{H_{2in}}$. The generated current density will be estimated by integrating the local current density in the electrode's surfaces, while heat generation and dissipation will be estimated by integrating the heat fluxes on the reactor volume.	

MARGIN OF ERROR	The accuracy of the simulations would depend on the available experimental data. Since this is a research project in which feasibility of the materials as new catalysts are being studied, error values around 20% after refining for all the magnitudes should be acceptable.
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5.4 Hybrid Machine Learning–DFT model

Machine learning methods are used in the project to complement and accelerate the physics-based modelling activities. By learning relationships between material composition and predicted properties, machine learning models can explore a much larger design space than would be feasible using first-principles simulations alone.

In this work, a **hybrid DFT–machine learning approach** is implemented to combine the high accuracy of electronic-structure simulations with the efficiency of data-driven prediction models.

Two main machine learning techniques are employed:

- **Gaussian Process Regression (GPR)**
- **Bayesian Optimisation (BO)**

The Gaussian Process model acts as a **surrogate model** for DFT simulations, learning the relationship between material descriptors and the properties calculated through first-principles modelling. Material compositions are represented numerically using physically motivated descriptors derived during data preprocessing.

Bayesian Optimisation is then used to guide the search for new candidate materials. Based on the surrogate model, the algorithm proposes new compositions expected to improve the optimisation objective.

The modelling workflow follows an iterative loop:

1. Train the machine learning model using an initial dataset that combines project data and information extracted from publicly available materials databases.
2. Use Bayesian Optimisation to identify promising candidate materials.
3. Evaluate these candidates using new DFT simulations.
4. Incorporate the new results into the training dataset to improve the predictive model.

This iterative process enables an efficient exploration of the materials design space while maintaining consistency with the underlying physical modelling framework.

Figure 5-6: Hybrid Machine Learning–DFT model (KNOW)

DATA-BASED MODEL(Hybrid DFT/ML Model): Machine Learning Integration (KNOW)	USER CASE	
	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE CALCULATED	Prediction of DFT-related quantities such as activation energies, adsorption enthalpies, and reaction steps energies.
	MATERIAL	Perovskite Oxides of the form $A_xA'_{1-x}B_yB'_{1-y}O_3$, with particular focus on the LSCF and LSFN system
	GEOMETRY	Atomic structure
	TIME LAPSE	NA (Static)
	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	NA
	PUBLICATIONS ON THIS DATAMINIG OPERATION	Unpublished yet

DATA-BASED MODEL(Hybrid DFT/ML Model): Machine Learning Integration (KNOW)	THE DATA-BASED MODEL	
	EQUATION TYPE AND NAME	Regression model based on Gaussian Processes and Bayesian Optimisation for experimental design
	DATABASE AND TYPE	Simulated data with DFT model (Model 1) and public data gathered from the Materials Project Database (https://next-gen.materialsproject.org/)
	EQUATION	<p style="text-align: center;">HYPOTHESIS</p> <p>The data is assumed to follow a multivariate Gaussian distribution with mean m and covariance function k:</p> $E(x) \sim \mathcal{GP}(m(x), k(x, x'))$
	PHYSICAL QUANTITIES	<p>Total energy E</p> <p>System descriptors x (features in Machine Learning terminology)</p>

DATA-BASED MODEL (Hybrid DFT/ML Model): Machine Learning Integration (KNOW)	COMPUTATIONAL DETAIL OF DATAMINING OPERATION	
	NUMERICAL OPERATIONS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feature Engineering: Converting composition strings and atomic structures into numerical features/descriptors Standardization: Transforming features and target quantities to have zero mean and unit variance Model Training: Computing similarities and performing matrix inversions within the Gaussian Process framework Model Prediction: Generating predictions for a selection of new materials Candidate Selection: Using Bayesian Optimisation to identify candidates for DFT calculations
SOFTWARE TOOL	Python	

	MARGIN OF ERROR	≈ 50 meV (1-2%) (estimated error of materials project data)
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6 Conclusions

This document presents the application of the MODA framework to structure and document the multiscale modelling workflow developed within the KNOWSKITE-X project.

By organising the modelling activities in a clear and consistent format, the MODA documentation facilitates communication between researchers working at different modelling scales and supports the integration of modelling results across the project.

The workflows and MODA fiches presented in this document provide a transparent description of the models used, the data exchanged between them, and the methodologies applied to simulate the behaviour of perovskite-based electrochemical systems. This structured documentation can support future research activities and contribute to the reproducibility and reuse of modelling workflows in related studies.